

Machine-actionable DMPs

What are Data Management Plans (DMPs)?

- ❖ **Data management plans (DMPs)** are “awareness tools” (Miksa et al. 2019) designed to “help researchers manage their data and ensure that it will be of high quality, accessible, and reusable” after a project ends (Miksa et al. 2019).
- ❖ **DMPs** typically contain the following information:
 - ❖ **Data:** What data are used and produced during the course of research activities
 - ❖ **Archiving:** Where the data will be archived
 - ❖ **Licenses:** Which licenses and constraints apply, and
 - ❖ **Credit:** To whom credit should be given
- ❖ **DMPs** describe the data and tools employed in scientific investigations as free-form text (Miksa et al. 2019).
- ❖ **While DMPs** have been in use since the 1960s, they are now increasingly required by funding bodies and institutions e.g., the European Commission.
- ❖ **The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship** (Wilkinson et al. 2016; 2018) call for DMPs to be machine-actionable (maDMPs) in order to comply with the principles of accessibility and interoperability to facilitate the integration with the broader research data management infrastructure (Miksa et al. 2019).
- ❖ **In** response to these developments, the Research Data Alliance developed the **RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable Data Management Plans (RDACS)**, the latest release of which (at the time of writing) is Version 1.1 from November 11, 2020.

Problems

Why should DMPs be machine-actionable?

DMPs are often created manually using checklists and online questionnaires, taking the form of (written) documents accompanying research proposals and project outputs. This has meant that extracting useful information from traditional free-text based DMPs is problematic.

Machine-Actionability: information that is consistently structured so that **machines can be programmed against such a structure**. Machine-actionable DMP (**maDMP**) is an **emerging standard for adding machine-actionable richness to data management plans** to enable a frictionless exchange of information across research tools and systems and eventually reduce the administrative burden.

10 Principles of Machine-actionability (Miksa et al. 2019)

- ❖ Integrate DMPs with the workflows of all stakeholders in the research data ecosystem
- ❖ Allow automated systems to act on behalf of stakeholders
- ❖ Make policies (also) for machines, not just for people
- ❖ Describe the components of the data management ecosystem for both machines and humans
- ❖ Use PIDs and controlled vocabularies
- ❖ Follow a common data model for maDMPs
- ❖ Make DMPs available for human and machine consumption
- ❖ Support data management evaluation and monitoring
- ❖ Make DMPs updatable, living, versioned documents
- ❖ Make DMPs publicly available